

NATIONAL CULTURAL CENTERS OPERATING IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN AND THEIR ROLE IN ENSURING INTER-NATIONAL HARMONY.

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Abstract: This article analyzes the role of national cultural centers operating in the Republic of Uzbekistan in society and their role in ensuring inter-ethnic harmony. Uzbekistan is a multinational state in which representatives of different nationalities and ethnic groups live in harmony. National cultural centers, in addition to preserving the culture, traditions and language of these nationalities and ethnic groups, and promoting their active participation in social life, serve to strengthen the atmosphere of mutual respect and cooperation in society. The article covers the areas of activity of these centers, their contribution to ensuring inter-ethnic stability and the support measures provided by the state. The importance of national cultural centers in preserving national values and unifying society is also widely analyzed.

Keywords: Uzbekistan, national cultural centers, interethnic harmony, social stability, cultural diversity, national values, mutual respect, cooperation, cultural heritage, social integration, civic solidarity, state support, interethnic relations, cultural ties, ethnic groups.

O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA FAOLIYAT KO'RSATUVCHI MILLIY MADANIY MARKAZLAR VA ULARNING MILLATLARARO TOTUVLIKNI TAMINLASHDA TUTGAN URNI.

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasida faoliyat yurituvchi milliy madaniy markazlarning jamiyatdagi o'rnini va ularning millatlararo totuvlikni ta'minlashdagi roli tahlil qilinadi. O'zbekiston ko'p millatli davlat bo'lib, unda turli millat va elatlar vakillari hamjihatlikda yashaydi. Milliy madaniy markazlar esa ushbu millat va elatlarning madaniyati, an'analari va tilini saqlash, ularning ijtimoiy hayotda faol ishtirok etishiga ko'maklashish bilan bir qatorda, jamiyatda o'zaro hurmat va

hamkorlik muhitini mustahkamlashga xizmat qiladi. Maqolada ushbu markazlarning faoliyat yo'nalishlari, ularning millatlararo barqarorlikni ta'minlashdagi hissasi va davlat tomonidan ko'rsatilayotgan qo'llab-quvvatlash choralari yoritiladi. Shuningdek, milliy madaniy markazlarning milliy qadriyatlarni asrab-avaylash va jamiyatni birlashtirishdagi ahamiyati keng tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: O'zbekiston, milliy madaniy markazlar, millatlararo totuvlik, ijtimoiy barqarorlik, madaniy xilma-xillik, milliy qadriyatlar, o'zaro hurmat, hamkorlik, madaniy meros, ijtimoiy integratsiya, fuqarolik birdamligi, davlat qo'llab-quvvatlovi, millatlararo munosabatlar, madaniy aloqalar, etnik guruhlar.

НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ КУЛЬТУРНЫЕ ЦЕНТРЫ, ДЕЙСТВУЮЩИЕ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН, И ИХ РОЛЬ В ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИИ МЕЖНАЦИОНАЛЬНОГО СОГЛАСИЯ.

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Аннотация: В статье анализируется роль национальных культурных центров, действующих в Республике Узбекистан, в обществе и их роль в обеспечении межнационального согласия. Узбекистан – многонациональное государство, где дружно проживают представители разных национальностей и народностей. Национальные культурные центры, помимо сохранения культуры, традиций и языка этих наций и народностей, способствуют их активному участию в общественной жизни, укреплению атмосферы взаимного уважения и сотрудничества в обществе. В статье рассматриваются направления деятельности этих центров, их вклад в обеспечение межэтнической стабильности, а также меры поддержки со стороны государства. Также будет подробно проанализировано значение национальных культурных центров в сохранении национальных ценностей и объединении общества.

Ключевые слова: Узбекистан, национальные культурные центры, межнациональное согласие, социальная стабильность, культурное многообразие, национальные ценности, взаимоуважение, сотрудничество, культурное наследие, социальная интеграция, гражданская солидарность, государственная поддержка, межнациональные отношения, культурные связи, этнические группы.

The Republic of Uzbekistan is a multinational state, where representatives of different nationalities and ethnic groups live in peace and harmony, contributing to the development of society. The role of national cultural centers in strengthening this interethnic harmony and stability is incomparable. These centers serve to preserve and develop the culture, traditions and customs of representatives of different nationalities, strengthen the atmosphere of mutual respect and cooperation, and ensure stability in society. The government of Uzbekistan actively supports the policy of interethnic harmony and solidarity and creates the necessary conditions for the effective functioning of national cultural centers. These centers serve as an important tool of public diplomacy and play an important role in strengthening friendly ties between nations. The first national cultural centers in our country were established in 1989 by Koreans, Kazakhs, Jews, and Armenians. The real development and prosperity of these centers began after our country gained its independence. During the years of independence, ample opportunities were created for their effective operation. If in 1992 there were 10 national-cultural centers, in 1995 their number reached 72, and by 2003 it reached 135. Today, the Committee on Interethnic Relations and Friendship with Foreign Countries cooperates with 150 national cultural centers, 38 friendship societies and 38 societies of compatriots abroad operating in our country. They consist of republican cultural centers, regional, city and district cultural centers. Ensuring the active participation of representatives of different nationalities living in the Republic of Uzbekistan in socio-political, spiritual-educational and cultural processes is one of the important areas of activity of national-cultural centers. The centers also carry out friendly cooperation with compatriots of nations in foreign countries, establish and develop cultural and educational ties. The Republican International Cultural Center, on the other hand, performs the task of strengthening solidarity and interethnic harmony among the citizens of the country. The main tasks of national-cultural centers have three directions:

- 1) restoring the language, culture, traditions and customs of each nation, reviving contacts and relations with the historical Motherland, and opening a wide path for the manifestation of national feelings;
- 2) recognizing independent Uzbekistan as one's true Motherland and serving it with gratitude and loyalty;
- 3) Living together with the Motherland, studying its culture, history and language, living in friendship, cooperation and harmony with the nation that gave its name to the independent state. The activities carried out in these three areas correspond to the requirements of modernizing social life and the development of interethnic relations.

Today, they include:

- studying their national history, culture, language, and traditions;
- mastering the secrets of national music, dance, and crafts;
- holding mass events and festivals dedicated to national holidays;
- organizing exhibitions dedicated to the life and work of artists, writers, poets, aqins and bakhshis, cultural and political figures of their historical homeland;
- holding meetings with people from their historical homeland has become a tradition.

National cultural centers operate within the republic, region, city, district and act as organizations that coordinate events held in these territorial units. At the same time, the centers also play the role of a kind of cultural and ideological center, uniting and directing representatives of different nationalities and ethnic groups around the strategic goals of Uzbekistan. Experienced, well-known scientists, intellectuals, and artists began to come to national cultural centers, and they began to form professional and amateur artistic associations. The activities of Russian, Korean, Crimean Tatar, Turkish, Kazakh, German, Tajik, and Uyghur groups were especially effective. Courses for studying the language and literature of a particular nation began to be opened at such centers. The activities of national cultural centers are coordinated by the Republican International Cultural Center, established by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 13, 1992. Interethnic harmony, international friendship, is one of the main ideas of the ideology of national independence. It is no exaggeration to say that the culture of interethnic dialogue is at an excellent level in our independent country. Because the friendly relations of Uzbeks with representatives of other nationalities are manifested in the form of indirect and direct dialogue. In the process of interethnic dialogue, as a representative of his nation, he performs a certain social function. As a result, he assimilates the spiritual values, manners, and culture of behavior accumulated by his people in the process of historical development. The role of national cultural centers in the development of such interethnic relations is very important.

National cultural centers (NCCs) operate on the basis of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the current laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan on public organizations, as well as their own charter. National cultural centers voluntarily unite citizens of Uzbekistan interested in studying, preserving and developing national culture, language, customs, traditions and customs characteristic of a particular nationality. They carry out their activities directly or through their branches in communities on the territory of Uzbekistan. By 2010, about 140 national cultural centers established by representatives of 27 nationalities operated in our republic. 28 MMM have republican status. 31 MMMs were established by Koreans, 23 MMMs by Russians, 10 MMMs by Tajiks, 9 MMMs by Kazakhs, 9 MMMs by Tatars (3 of which

are Tatar-Bashkir MMMs), 8 MMMs among Azerbaijanis, 7 among Turkmens, 6 among Ukrainians and Kyrgyz, 5 among Turks and European Jews.

Germans, Poles and Armenians have established 4 MMMs each. Uyghurs and Bukhara Jews have 3 MMMs each. Belarusians and Crimean Tatars have 2 MMMs each. Arabs, Bulgarians, Bashkirs, Greeks, Georgians, Lithuanians, Karakalpaks, Chinese and Dungans have established 1 MMM each. 74 people from the Republican International Cultural Center and MMM activists have been awarded high state awards. Including, 32 people were awarded the Order of Friendship, 2 people were awarded the Order of Labor Glory, 13 people were awarded the Medal of Glory. 7 people were awarded honorary titles, 17 people were awarded Certificates of Honor of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Among the awardees are representatives of 24 nationalities. Today, Hero of Uzbekistan Vera Borisovna Pak is a member of the board of the Khorezm regional Korean MMM. The head of the Republican Russian National Cultural Center Svetlana Ivanovna Gerasimova is a senator, People's Teacher of Uzbekistan. 12 programs and broadcasts are conducted on television and radio (Uzbek, Karakalpak, Russian, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Tajik, Turkmen, Tatar, Uyghur, Azerbaijani). Newspapers are published in 10 languages (Uzbek, Karakalpak, Russian, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Tajik, Turkmen, Ukrainian, English), and magazines are published in 8 languages. (Uzbek, Karakalpak, Russian, English, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Tajik, Turkmen). Secondary and higher education is carried out in 7 languages: Uzbek, Karakalpak, Russian, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Tajik, Turkmen.

In particular, it is advisable to organize a large-scale friendship festival, which is being held in cooperation with the RBMM and the MMM under the slogan "Uzbekistan - our common home" and promote it through the media. In 2013, 162 creative associations representing 120 nationalities and ethnic groups participated in the friendship festival "Uzbekistan - our common home", 14 of which were awarded honorary certificates, 4 third, 3 second, 2 first places and prizes. The performed work, melody, song, dance were evaluated according to whether they reflect the achievements of the renewing country and homeland.

National cultural centers are actively participating in the formation and development of a democratic legal state in the modernization processes. In his congratulatory message on the 10th anniversary of the establishment of the Russian National Cultural Center, our First President says: "Today, it is difficult to overestimate the positive and multifaceted work carried out by national cultural centers in our country to strengthen mutual trust between people, to create an atmosphere of confidence in the future, to educate the younger generation in the spirit that they should be smarter, more enlightened, stronger and, of course, happier than us."

In connection with the declaration of 2015 by the First President of our country as the Year of “Respect for the Elderly,” the MMMs are planning to hold literary evenings, meetings, anniversaries and celebrations dedicated to great people of different nations. For example, the Russian MMM and its regional branches are planning to hold an evening dedicated to M. Lermontov, L. Tolstoy, M. Svetaeva, A. Akhmatova, A. Navoi, the Ukrainian MMM is planning to hold an evening dedicated to T. Shevchenko, Gogol, and the Tatar MMM is planning to hold an evening dedicated to the life and work of the Tatar writer and poet Abdulla Tokai.

The centers' activities to strengthen interethnic harmony in Uzbekistan are also distinguished by their diversity. For example, in this direction, the German MMM has staged performances glorifying friendship between peoples through the “Vdoknovenie” youth theater organized by it, while the Uyghur MMM has been organizing roundtable discussions in Andijan and other regions on the topic “Uzbekistan is our common home”. In order to contribute to the patriotic upbringing of young people, the RBMM, in collaboration with the MMM, organized an excursion to Samarkand in order to familiarize young people of different nationalities with our rich history by taking them to museums such as “History of Uzbekistan” and “History of the Timurids”. In May 2014, the Greek MMM organized an excursion to Samarkand to familiarize their young people with the ancient cities of Uzbekistan and introduced them to the rich history of the Uzbek people. In 2014 and 2016, together with the RBMM and MMM, they celebrated national holidays such as Russian Easter, Bashkir-Tatar Sabantoy, Korean Tano and Chusok, and German Ostern on a large scale with the participation of representatives of different nationalities and ethnic groups.

In 2014, the final stage of the Korean culture festival “Zdrastvuy, Tano” was held in the G.Ghulom Park, and in October, the Festival of Friendship between Uzbekistan and the Republic of Korea was held. The German MMM held the Republican Youth Festival of German Culture for the fourth time. The Bulgarian MMM organized a sports dance evening called “New Asian Style”, in which citizens of Uzbekistan of different nationalities participated.

Since 2004-2015, the RBMM, together with the MMM, organized 28 exhibitions of works by artists of different nationalities living in the republic under the slogan “Uzbekistan is my Homeland”. In particular, they:

- “Winter Vernissage”, “My Native City” in 2004;- Graphic works by Yanis Salpinkidis on the theme “My Native Uzbekistan” by the Greek MMM in 2005;
- 2007: color paintings on the themes of “Spring Vernissage”, “Navruz”, “Spring Colors”;
- 2011: works by Margarita Shuvalova on the theme of “Spring, zhenshina, sveti”;

- 2014: exhibitions “Joy of Pure Love” dedicated to the Sazanov dynasty and “I Love You, My Country” were organized.

Since 2017, a new era has begun in the activities of the National Cultural Centers. In 2017, various events were held in all regions of our country on the occasion of the 25th anniversary of the Republican International Cultural Center. Over the years of independence, more than a hundred activists of the Republican International Cultural Center and national cultural centers have been awarded honorary titles, orders and medals. It is worth noting that 14 of our citizens, representing different nationalities, were awarded the high title of Hero of Uzbekistan. I know many of you personally, most of you through your appearances on television and in the press, and today I am happy to present high awards of our Motherland to more than 20 more enterprising and selfless compatriots who are an example to others and make a worthy contribution to strengthening the unity and cohesion of our people. Among them are our compatriots Nurkul Bazarbayeva, an activist of the Karakalpak National Cultural Center in the Konimekh district of the Navoi region, Sergey Mironov, deputy director of the Republican International Cultural Center, Anisya Gataullina, chairman of the Tatar National Cultural Center in the Yangiyul district of the Tashkent region, Faina Golubsova, chairman of the Russian National Cultural Center in the Syrdarya region, Polatbek Izyumov, chairman of the Kazakh National Cultural Center in the Khorezm region, Oleg Kim, chairman of the Korean National Cultural Center in the Jizzakh region, Semyon Abdurakhmonov, chairman of the Jewish National Cultural Center in the Fergana region, Lidiya Dovidaitis, chairman of the Lithuanian National Cultural Center in Tashkent, Natalya Kaiser, chairman of the German National Cultural Center in the Samarkand region, Olga Mironets, chairman of the Ukrainian National Cultural Center "Slavutich" in the Nukus city, and Abdurasul Ergashev, chairman of the Tajik National Cultural Center in the Kashkadarya region. Also, Nina Shubnikova, deputy chairman of the Belarusian National Cultural Center "Svitanak" in Tashkent, and Nina Shubnikova, deputy chairman of the Arab National Cultural Center in the Kashkadarya region Niyozmuhammad Panjiyev, Deputy Chairman of the Turkish National Cultural Center in Bukhara region Juma Shukurov, Artistic Director of the "Azerbaijan Girls" Ensemble of the Azerbaijani National Cultural Center of the Republic Kaykep Aliyeva, An activist of the Turkmen National Cultural Center of the Republic of Karakalpakstan Arazmukhammet Abayev, An activist of the Kyrgyz National Cultural Center in Andijan region Umutkhan Mamataliyeva, An activist of the Armenian National Cultural Center of the Republic Georgiy Saakov and others were also awarded state awards. With their joint efforts, they are fulfilling the most important task, namely,

making a worthy contribution to the development of our country, strengthening its spiritual and humanitarian foundations.

In conclusion, the national cultural centers operating in the Republic of Uzbekistan play an important role in strengthening interethnic harmony and solidarity in the country. They help representatives of different nationalities to preserve their national culture, language and traditions, and serve to strengthen the bonds of friendship between them. At the same time, these centers also carry out activities such as developing cultural and educational ties with compatriots abroad, promoting national art and traditions. Ensuring interethnic harmony in Uzbekistan is one of the priorities of state policy, and constant support and conditions are created for the effective functioning of national cultural centers. Their activities serve to ensure the peaceful coexistence of representatives of different nationalities in the country and the social stability of society. Therefore, the role of national cultural centers is incomparable, and their development will help to further strengthen interethnic friendship and harmony in the future.

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